

Feed additives for methane mitigation: Recommendations for identification and selection of bioactive compounds to develop antimethanogenic feed additives

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ABSTRACT

Despite the increasing interest in developing anti-methanogenic additives to reduce enteric methane (CH₄) emissions and the extensive research conducted over the last decades, the global livestock industry has a very limited number of antimethanogenic feed additives (AMFA) available that can deliver substantial reduction, and they have generally not reached the market yet. This work provides technical recommendations and guidelines for conducting tests intended to screen the potential to reduce, directly or indirectly, enteric CH₄ of compounds before they can be further assessed in *in vivo* conditions. The steps involved in this work cover the discovery, isolation, and identification of compounds capable of affecting CH₄ production by rumen microbes, followed by *in vitro* laboratory testing of potential candidates. The finding of new bioactive compounds as AMFA can be based on 2 approaches: empirical and mechanistic. The empirical approach involves obtaining and screening compounds present in databases and repositories that potentially possess the desired effect but have not

yet been tested, screening natural sources of secondary compounds such as plants, fungi, and algae for their antimethanogenic effects, or examining compounds with antimethanogenic effect on microbes in other research domains outside the rumen. In contrast, the mechanistic approach is the theoretical process of discovery new bioactive compounds based on existing knowledge of a biological target or process. The *in vitro* methodologies reviewed include examining effects at the subcellular level, in single pure cultures of methanogens and examining in more complex mixed rumen microbial populations. Simple *in vitro* methodologies (subcellular assessments and batch culture) allow testing a large number of compounds, whereas more complex systems simulating the rumen microbial ecosystem can test a limited number of candidates but provide better insight about the antimethanogenic efficacy. This work collated the main advantages, limitations, and technical recommendations associated with each step and methodology use during the identification and screening of AMFA candidates.

Key words: *in silico*, docking, *in vitro*, methane, rumen

INTRODUCTION

There is increasing interest and need in reducing GHG emissions worldwide, with enteric methane (CH₄) from ruminants being one of the main targets (Jackson et al.,

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2020). The modulation of rumen fermentation through feeding practices and in particular the use of antimethanogenic feed additives (AMFA) has been identified as one of the most promising strategies to reduce CH₄ emissions from ruminants (Arndt et al., 2022). However, despite extensive research conducted over the last decades, the global livestock industry has a very limited number of AMFA available that can deliver substantial reduction and they have generally not reached the market yet (Hegarty et al., 2021). Some of the main constraints are related to poor understanding of the chemistry of the compounds and the efficacy to reduce CH₄ production without compromising overall rumen function. Potential risks associated with their use needs to be also fully assessed (Hegarty et al., 2021).

As the *in vivo* research is laborious, costly, and has many challenges, such as supply of material and ethical considerations, the first steps in developing AMFA usually involve location, isolation, and selection of compounds capable of affecting CH₄ production by rumen microbes, followed by *in vitro* laboratory testing of potential candidates.

Bioactive compounds able to inhibit methanogenesis can be classified by mode of action: direct or indirect inhibition of methanogenesis (Belanche et al., 2025). Antimethanogenic compounds can inhibit the methanogenesis directly by targeting enzymes and co-factors within the specific methanogenesis pathway (Liu et al., 2011; Patra and Puchala, 2023), or the biosynthesis of specific membrane lipids (Liu et al., 2011). In contrast, indirect inhibitors (Fouts et al., 2022) include compounds that modify the rumen ecosystem, creating unfavorable conditions, for example, by reducing the amount of hydrogen produced (van Gastelen et al., 2024), or competing with methanogenesis as alternative hydrogen sinks (Malik et al., 2015). Although direct CH₄ inhibitors generally promote greater reductions, indirect inhibitors may also contribute to increase yield and thus, decrease emissions intensity (Hegarty et al., 2021); therefore, when applicable, they are also considered in this work. Antimethanogenic compounds can also be classified by origin: naturally or synthetically produced. The naturally produced compounds have been identified in plants, macroalgae, fungi, and microorganisms, among other biological sources (Honan et al., 2022). Conversely, a synthetic compound refers to a substance with a manufactured rather than biogenic origin, such as 3-nitrooxypropanol (3-NOP) or synthetic halogenated compounds (Patra and Puchala, 2023).

In the past 25 yr, around 3,000 peer-reviewed papers reported *in vitro* screening for CH₄ mitigation effects in ruminants (when term “*in vitro* methane rumen” was searched in ScienceDirect; <https://www.sciencedirect.com>). *In vitro* testing allows the antimethanogenic ef-

fects of various products in controlled laboratory settings to be assessed in a relatively short time, offering first insight on efficacy and mechanisms of action but also selectivity of compounds in suppressing CH₄ production without adversely affecting other microbial activities (Bodas et al., 2008; Durmic et al., 2010). The *in vitro* testing can be coupled with isolation of active compound(s), which may involve the enrichment or separation from a complex matrix, screening of enriched fractions or individual compounds, and assigning the activity to a specific compound. Although there are obvious advantages and importance of *in silico* and *in vitro* testing in the development of AMFA, consideration should be given to a set of guidelines to identify the main aspects that must be appropriately covered during the first development stages.

This work aims to provide guidelines on the processes involved in the initial steps of developing AMFA, with recommendations on the approaches and methodologies to be used to identify and select candidates for further evaluation (Table 1). The process of developing AMFA then follows with validating the identified candidates in animal testing and applying for authorization of the claimed effect (Hristov et al., 2025; Tricarico et al., 2025), to be supported with quantification of AMFA efficacy in modeling studies (del Prado et al., 2025; Dijkstra et al., 2025) and gained understanding of AMFA mode of action (Belanche et al., 2025).

FINDING BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS

Finding bioactive compounds that can be developed as AMFA can be based on 2 approaches: empirical and mechanistic (Figure 1). The empirical approach involves obtaining and experimentally screening compounds present in different sources of information (databases, repositories, traditional knowledge) suspected to possess the desired effect, or screening natural sources of secondary compounds such as plants, fungi, and algae for their antimethanogenic effects. The mechanistic approach is the theoretical process of finding new bioactive compounds based on existing knowledge of a biological target or process.

Empirical Approach

The first step in this approach commonly involves finding published evidence of specific (i.e., antimethanogenic) or general (i.e., antimicrobial) bioactive direct or indirect effects, by searching the scientific literature, databases, patents, reports, or other curated repositories. The next step requires obtaining bioactive material from the identified source, such as plants from plant collections or wild populations, feed additives and supplements, byproducts from the agroindustry, natural product librar-

Table 1. Summary of recommendations using different methodologies for the identification and selection of bioactive compounds to develop antimethanogenic feed additives

Methodology	Recommendation
Discovering bioactive compounds	<p>Empirical approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search for candidates with specific or general bioactive effects. Broaden the search by seeking candidates being explored in other disciplines. • The isolation of pure bioactive compounds usually requires multiple rounds of separation using chromatographic techniques coupled with a confirmation bioassay. <p>Mechanistic approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the target within the unique methanogens' chemistry and metabolic processes (i.e., Mer and RFAP). • Obtain the structure of the targeted protein or enzyme (from databases of experimentally derived crystal structures or modeled with computational tools). • Carefully select the library or use curated libraries, as the targeted library is key in developing initial hits. • Evaluate chemically diverse scaffolds in natural products or phenotypic libraries made of approved drugs and annotated potent inhibitors. • Perform in-depth in silico docking process and programming combining computational tools and docking studies. • Confirm bioavailability of selected candidate(s).
In vitro testing	<p>Testing effects at subcellular level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce enough cell mass (or enzyme material) to allow sufficient target protein to be present in cell extracts or to be fully purified. • Consider the best methanogens to grow in the laboratory facilities to yield maximum material. • Combinations of linear and steps gradient will be needed (run on fast protein liquid chromatography equipment) to properly separate the enzymes. • Enzymology assays to establish the inhibition kinetics need to be complemented by other methods (GC, MS, colorimetry) to identify the products obtained from the reaction. <p>Testing effects in pure culture of methanogens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methanogens require exclusion of oxygen to grow, a special mix of gas (H₂ and CO₂ 80:20 or 50:50) and there are additional grow requirements specific for each species. • Run the test on a suit of methanogen species that represent the most abundant ones in the rumen across the main phylogenetic clades and specific metabolic features. <p>Testing effects in a mixed rumen microbial community in batch culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider the potential offered by this approach to do initial evaluation covering diverse dietary conditions, dosages, or formulations. • Donor animal should be fed a diet similar to that used as a substrate in vitro to provide a more adapted rumen microbiota. • Technical recommendations on inoculum processing, buffer, and headspace gas composition are provided in Yáñez-Ruiz et al. (2016). <p>More recommendations in “overarching methodological considerations.”</p> <p>Testing compounds in continuous and semicontinuous culture systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider actions to maintain protozoal population as much as possible in the culture. • Technical recommendations on inoculum processing, buffer, pore size in incubation bags, and dilution rate are provided in Deitmers et al. (2022). <p>More recommendations in “overarching methodological considerations.”</p> <p>Experimental design and statistical analyses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For dose-response evaluations, include a minimum of 3 levels (+ control) to assess linear, quadratic, and cubic (4 minimum) components of the response to incremental amounts of each compound evaluated using orthogonal polynomial contrasts. • In RUSITEC, adapt the allocation of treatments to the number of units available using a randomized complete block design. <p>Selecting dosage of candidate compound(s)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select at least 3 or 4 doses with 5- to 10-fold increase to ensure that both lack of effect and overall reduction of fermentation are covered. • Dosage recommended considering the mode of action: (1) for compounds that modify the fermentation profile: <0.1% in relation to substrate DM; (2) for H₂ acceptors: around 1% to 2% of substrate DM; and (3) for compounds that directly inhibit methanogenic archaea: <100 mg/kg of substrate or 25 to 150 µM.
Overarching methodological considerations	<p>Transforming dosage from in vitro batch to continuous cultures or to in vivo considering the mode of action: (1) for direct effect on ruminal microbiota dose better referred to ruminal volume; and (2) for H₂ acceptors the concentration could be related to dietary DM.</p> <p>Testing combination of different candidate compound(s)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore combination of candidates with different mode of action. • Performed this assessment once optimal inclusion levels of each compound have been defined. • Longer culture systems than batch culture may be required to ensure adaptation to interactions.

Continued

Table 1 (Continued). Summary of recommendations using different methodologies for the identification and selection of bioactive compounds to develop antimethanogenic feed additives

Methodology	Recommendation
	<p>Delivery of candidate compound(s)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For liquid format: (1) water soluble: pipetting directly the volume corresponding to the experimental dosage into the in vitro vessel; (2) not soluble in water: diluted in ethanol or dimethyl sulfoxide at the necessary concentration to achieve the final dose (include 10 μL solution/mL culture, and an equivalent amount of solvent has to be added to the control treatment bottles). Inoculation time: (1) in batch: inoculate immediately before adding the rumen fluid to initiate the incubation; (2) in fermenters: adapt to feeding times per day. • For solid format: (1) in batch culture: weight in vessels well before initiating the incubations; (2) in fermenters: mixed with the substrate at every feeding time. <p>When and how to measure methane and units to express the production</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methods: (1) in pure cultures of methanogens conducted in Hungate tubes: measured in headspace gas samples taken every 2 to 3 d; (2) in batch culture: at different incubation times (CH_4 production kinetics) with a minimum of 2 measurements (first at 12 h, second at the end of incubation); and (3) fermenters: measure every 24 h by sampling gas from the collection bags. • Units: referred CH_4 production to a value indicative of fermentation extent (preferably total VFA production, alternatively degraded DM).

ies, as well as commercially available compounds and existing drugs (Figure 1). The CH_4 -mitigating evidence does not necessarily have to be related to enteric CH_4 , and compounds with proven activity against nonrumen methanogens (e.g., in manure, rice fields, or other environments) are also potentially of interest for targeting rumen methanogens or indirectly through modification of rumen fermentation. Traditionally, this initial step is followed by laboratory in vitro testing of selected candidates for their antimethanogenic effects (see following sections), and then by efforts to isolate the compound(s) responsible for the effect and to characterize the target mechanism and cellular processes responsible for such CH_4 reduction (Flachowsky and Lebzien, 2012), which is not the focus of this work. Detailed description and recommendations on how to identify the mode of action of AMFA can be found in a separate work in this special issue (Belanche et al., 2025).

The empirical approach can be conducted by directly screening material obtained from collections of plants, fungi, or algae thought to contain secondary compounds in the in vitro mixed rumen cultures. This approach relies on increasing the chance of finding biological materials that inhibit methanogenesis by screening a large number of materials (Bodas et al., 2012) and may lead to finding compounds previously not known to inhibit methanogenesis (Macheboeuf et al., 2008; Durmic et al., 2014; Joch et al., 2016). It may also be useful in finding a natural source that contains a previously known antimethanogenic compound. For example, it has long been known that haloalkanes such as bromoform inhibit methanogenesis (Bauchop, 1967), and in recent years, this compound has been found responsible for the antimethanogenic effect of *Asparagopsis taxiformis* (Machado et al., 2016).

As natural sources of compounds are often complex mixtures, typically containing thousands of different molecules, specific procedures are needed to isolate compounds, which may be then used directly or as platforms for developing new analogs with enhanced properties (Najmi et al., 2022). The isolation of pure bioactive compounds usually requires multiple rounds of separation using chromatographic techniques, coupled with a confirmation bioassay that leads to the isolation of plant extracts containing the most active fractions or ultimately pure compounds in a process called “bioassay-guided fractionation” (Mani et al., 2022). In the process, only plant fractions exhibiting activity are progressed until the single pure compound or defined mix of compounds responsible for the target biological activity are identified. Bioassay for testing inhibition of CH_4 production commonly relies on using methanogen(s) pure cultures (Ungerfeld et al., 2004) or mixed culture of rumen microbes (Yáñez-Ruiz et al., 2016), as described and discussed below.

APPROACHES FOR SCREENING BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS

Figure 1. Alternative approaches for finding of bioactive compounds for the development of antimethanogenic feed additives. Created by F. Garcia and Sabrina Garay; used with permission.

The chemical characterization and structural elucidation of the pure compound(s) can be performed via 1-dimensional and 2-dimensional (2D) nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR), MS, liquid chromatography coupled with MS, high-resolution MS analyses, and with the help of additional spectroscopic (infrared and UV spectroscopy), or derivatization methods to elucidate stereochemistry (Batista et al., 2018). Mass spectroscopy can be performed with very small amounts of compounds and is widely available, whereas NMR

spectroscopy is also widely available but will require large amounts (500 μL for one sample) in the mM concentration range (>1 mM). The NMR spectral data are helpful to identify the functional groups, such as -OH, -CHO, -NH₂, -NH-, OCH₃, and so on, and compounds, including sugars, phenolics, steroids, terpenoids, and fatty acid esters. For more complex structure higher frequency NMR equipment need to be used (600–800 MHz) to be able to separate all the NMR peaks. If that is not possible, 2D techniques will need to be applied. Depen-

dent on the elemental analysis, different types of NMR can be performed on top of the ^1H NMR, such as ^{13}C -, ^{14}N -, and ^{15}F -NMR. The NMR measurements will also be essential to determine the configuration of stereoisomers present in the compound. Conversely, when the overall structure is known, the different stereoisomers could be synthesized, and their respective spectra compared with the isolated compound. If the compound can be crystallized, X-ray diffraction can also be used to obtain the 3-dimensional (**3D**) structure of the compound. In addition to the antimethanogenic activity, the decision on which pure compound(s) to progress with may also be driven by other characteristics of the molecule, evaluated, for instance, by MS/MS-guided molecular networking (Nonthias et al., 2018). Additional criteria to be considered are described in the “Other Criteria to Progress with AMFA Candidates” section.

Advantages. The empirical approach allows obtaining and testing a relatively large and diverse number of candidates in a short time.

Limitations. The AMFA candidate present in the parent material forms part of complex mixtures of compounds and may be present in low amounts, so that the quantities of parent material required for extraction and testing can be considerable and difficult to obtain. Although the parent material can be employed without isolating or purifying the active compound, the presence of other compounds in that material may significantly influence the outcomes and introduce additional complexities that can hinder claims of the AMFA mixed product. Thus, access to specialized equipment and adequate methods for fractionation and purification is recommended for efficient processing.

Mechanistic Approach

This approach relies on combining the use of computational tools (in silico) and docking studies, using a modeling technique to predict how target enzymes interact with candidate molecules, and then synthesizing the candidate compounds to be tested (Figure 1). The process of identifying candidate molecules to develop AMFA in this approach can start by targeting methanogens and their unique cellular processes, chemistry, enzymes, and coenzymes involved in CH_4 production, as well as cell wall structures that can be exploited as targets for AMFA development (Lyu et al., 2018; Subedi et al., 2021).

There are several potential starting points for drug discovery, such as using either experimentally derived crystal structures, of which to date over 5,887 archaeal protein structures are freely available online (RCSB Protein Data Bank; <https://www.rcsb.org/>), or modeled structures that can be developed using highly intuitive, freely available online tools such as AlphaFold2

(Mirdita et al., 2022). There are also several in silico screening platforms, such as the Maestro Schrödinger suite, Molsoft (Cardozo et al., 1995; Abagyan et al., 1997; Neves et al., 2012), AutoDock (Forli et al., 2016), and Gold (Verdonk et al., 2003), which provide a fast and cost-effective mechanism to speed up the drug discovery process. All these platforms offer in-depth in silico docking processes and programming that may include protein bioinformatics, modeling, minimization and dynamics, compound library analysis and editing, 3D visualization and ligand building capabilities, pharmacophore-led inhibitor design, and quantitative structure–activity relationship models.

One strategy uses in silico screening of compounds available in the libraries, which can potentially interfere in the final step in the methanogenesis pathways. This strategy has most often centered on methyl-coenzyme M reductase (**Mcr**; Arokiyaraj et al., 2019; Khusro et al., 2020; Dinakarkumar et al., 2021), the enzyme responsible for the final step of CH_4 formation (Ermler et al., 1997; Deppenmeier, 2002), in which the methyl group carried by coenzyme M (**CoM**) is reduced to CH_4 . Even though hits derived from library screens are difficult to move forward in an in vivo application, 3-NOP is one notable exception (Hristov et al., 2015; Duin et al., 2016); it is now going into market, showing that Mcr is a relevant molecular target in CH_4 mitigation. This is further illustrated by the long line of CoM (and coenzyme B) analogs, such as allyl-S-CoM, cyano-S-CoM, or bromomethanesulfonate, which were developed 15 yr before the first crystal structure for Mcr was available (Wackett et al., 1987; Goenrich et al., 2004). Similarly, 4-(β -D-ribofuranosyl) aminobenzene-5'-phosphate synthase (**RFAP**) is another enzyme unique to methanogen growth and energy metabolism (Dumitru and Ragsdale, 2004; White, 2011). As with Mcr and the development of coenzyme-based inhibitors, early inhibitors of RFAP were N-substituted structural analogs of the substrate para-aminobenzoic acid (**pABA**; Dumitru et al., 2003), without the knowledge of an enzyme structure to guide development. Using these types of inhibitors, structural modifications in the parent coenzyme or substrate can be readily followed up using additional in silico modifications at the target site and, with the identification of structure–activity relationship models, can lead to more potent molecules. Other target enzymes include methyl-tetrahydromethanopterin: CoM methyltransferase and heterodisulfide reductase (Hedderich et al., 1990). These and some other targets are discussed in more detail in another paper in this Special Issue (Belanche et al., 2025).

The aforementioned Mcr docking studies all showed that targeted library selection is key in developing initial hits. Unlike in silico library screening of the past, which involved compound library screens as simple compen-

diums of collected structures, most, if not all, commercially available libraries for in vitro or in silico analysis follow the customary “rule of 5” (Lipinski et al., 2001). This considers a compound’s druggability, by assessing the following key components (all being multiples of 5): the presence of no more than 5 H-bond donors, no more than 10 H-bond acceptors, molecular weight <500 Dalton, and calculated Log P that does not exceed 5 (with P, the octanol-water partition coefficient). Moreover, curated bioactive libraries can also be purchased allowing for finding of molecules that can be fast tracked (e.g., US Food & Drug Administration approved compounds) or avoided in larger screening practices (PAINS libraries; Baell and Holloway, 2010). Use of nitro-based organic molecules in the inhibition of methanogenesis is well known (Anderson et al., 2006, 2008; Saengkerdsut et al., 2006; Patra and Puchala, 2023) and have not been fully considered in modern screening studies; careful consideration should be given with respect to solubility and melting point, vapor pressure, and stability if the end product is likely to be formulated as a bolus.

An alternative strategy for high-quality leads is to evaluate chemically diverse scaffolds, which can be found among natural product libraries or phenotypic libraries made of approved drugs and annotated potent inhibitors (Spear and Brown, 2017). Although these parameters may be focused on a single enzyme target in silico, the development of small-scale in vitro screening of methanogens and CH₄ production means multiple enzymes can be assessed using these enriched libraries (Muetzel et al., 2014, 2018; Weimar et al., 2017). The selection criteria for compounds to test from in silico screening begins with the selection of a (often) commercial library made up of diverse (pharmacokinetically sound) chemotypes, targeted libraries with content known to affect particular enzyme function, or curated libraries of natural products, functional classes, or small chemical building blocks. We recommend basing the ultimate choice on whether the enzyme has been thoroughly characterized and substrates are known, whether inhibitors already exist and a new chemical platform is desired, or whether there is an immediate commercial need (approved drugs) or agronomical application where natural product libraries could be best. Each in silico platform has unique functions to process, score, energetically refine, and orient on each new compound and receptor complex, ranking the top “hitters” by rewarding Van der Waals energy interactions, lipophilicity/hydrophobic interactions and hydrogen bonding. Similarly, compounds are penalized based on steric clashes with amino acid sidechains and conformational strain of the compound within the receptor. The top-ranked compounds are then visually inspected within the active site, and molecular interactions are assessed for fit (in

some cases active site per residue scoring should also be considered) before making a selection.

Advantages. The mechanistic approach allows unlimited search and a relatively fast and high-throughput discovery, analysis, and development of methanogen-specific inhibitors. It could also lead to finding novel compounds.

Limitations. Sophisticated equipment and specific expertise are required. Potential antimethanogenic candidates for testing may not be available from natural sources, may be unknown, or if known, the candidates may still need to be isolated from parent material. Alternatively, they may have to be synthesized, imposing further complexity, with some compounds being difficult or expensive to synthesize in sufficient amounts. Some AMFA candidates identified through this approach may still have a low bioavailability in the cell, and a mutation of the transporter can make the cell resistant against the candidate.

IN VITRO TESTING

Once AMFA candidates have been identified, the next step is to evaluate experimentally the antimethanogenic activity considering different factors (e.g., dosage, formulation, interaction with diet and effects on other rumen fermentation variables). There is an array of in vitro methodologies that can be used for this purpose, spanning from examining effects at the subcellular level in a single microbial species to examining effects in more complex mixed rumen microbial populations, as described below and illustrated in Figure 2.

Testing Effects at Subcellular Level

Testing at subcellular level involves study of the effects of the selected candidate on the biological process or target for which it was identified (e.g., testing inhibition of enzymes derived from methanogen cells by enzymology assays). The first step is to produce cell mass (or enzyme material) that allows enough of the target protein to be present in cell extracts or to be fully purified. Methanogens have to be propagated and enzymes purified under strict exclusion of oxygen, and some of the target enzymes have to be purified. The doubling time and growth requirements (i.e., oxygen sensitivity, substrates, or incubation conditions during pure culture propagation) vary for the different methanogens; therefore, their characteristics need to be considered for the selection of the methanogenic species to use in the test. *Methanothermobacter marburgensis* (Duin et al., 2011) and *Methanothermobacter thermoautotrophicus* are 2 of the fastest-growing methanogens and most commonly used in these types of studies. Typically, these can reach a maximal optical density (OD) at 568 nm

IN VITRO TESTING OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS

Figure 2. In vitro methods for the evaluation of bioactive compounds selected for the development of antimethanogenic feed additives. Created by F. Garcia and Sabrina Garay; used with permission.

of 8 to 10 in 1 to 2 d at 65°C. For the 2 methanogens for which genetic systems are available, *Methanococcus marisaludis* (Sarmiento et al., 2011) and *Methanosarcina acetivorans* (Buan et al., 2011), longer growth

times (at 37°C) are needed (3–6 d) and a much lower OD is reached (0.6 to 0.8). Culturing methanogens in pure culture is further discussed in following section and in Belanche et al. (2025).

Depending on the abundance of the enzyme or protein of interest in the methanogen cultures, assays may be performed with cell extracts or the target may need to be isolated in higher purity. As mentioned in the previous section, although the Mcr has often been the main focus, several other targets are available. In several of the methanogens the Mcr content was found to be 10% of the total soluble protein in the cell (Gendron and Allen, 2022). The Mcr from several microorganisms can be purified with 2 ammonium sulfate precipitation steps (i.e., 70 mL and 100 mL/100 mL of microbial suspension) followed by one ion-exchange chromatography step (Duin et al., 2011). Enrichment of the partner enzyme heterodisulfide reductase, for example, requires multiple purification steps on 4 different columns (Hedderich et al., 1990). To properly separate enzymes with very similar properties, combinations of linear and step gradients will be needed that typically are run on fast protein liquid chromatography equipment.

To identify the enzyme fractions that show the desired activity, each will have to be assayed. For most of these enzymes, including Mcr and Hdr, their substrates are available commercially and need to be synthesized. Coenzyme B, which is needed for both activity assays, requires a 5-step synthesis (Duin et al., 2011). Access to NMR is required to assess the purity of the intermediate and final compounds.

With the semi-pure or pure enzyme in hand, inhibitor assays can be performed to establish enzyme inhibition kinetics. The assays are used to first establish the V_{max} , K_m , and k_{cat} values of the target enzyme followed by changes in these values as well as the determination of a K_i in the presence of inhibitors. Detection of product formation or disappearance of reactant can be done by determining concentration with colorimetry, GC (CH_4 or H_2 production), HPLC, MS, or NMR (Duin et al., 2016). These techniques can also be used to detect and characterize possible inhibitor breakdown products. The molecule 3-NOP, for example, is broken down into nitrite and 1,3-propanediol. Any products that are formed then need to be evaluated for toxicity. Assays at the subcellular level provide a proof of concept that the AMFA being tested has the capacity to inhibit their molecular target outside or inside the microbial cell, as described in Belanche et al. (2025). A wide variety of chromatography columns will be needed to be able to isolate the target enzyme or protein. The successfully screened compounds should be further tested against whole cells; enzymology assays can be skipped in the initial testing phase but might be required for describing mechanisms of action as part of the registration process and eventually for authorization by authorities (Tricarico et al., 2025).

Advantages. Testing at the subcellular level allows for the determination of enzyme activity, inhibition

kinetics, and inhibition mechanism. Additionally, it provides valuable information about potentially toxic byproducts, particularly if the inhibition stems from a specific reaction.

Limitations. The approach requires properly separated and purified enzymes. If substrates for the target enzyme are not commercially available, they need to be synthesized. Because methanogens and most of the enzymes to be tested are highly oxygen sensitive, special equipment is needed to purify proteins and handle samples under exclusion of oxygen.

Testing Effect in Pure Culture of Methanogens

The antimethanogenic effect of identified compounds can also be tested using *in vitro* assays with methanogen species grown in pure culture (Janssen and Frenzel, 1997), to evaluate the extent of the effect and sensitivity of different rumen methanogen species (Ungerfeld et al., 2004; Martínez-Fernández et al., 2014; Romero et al., 2023a). This allows distinction between static and cidal effects (Banik et al., 2016) and establishment of potential dose-response (Martínez-Fernández et al., 2014; Duin et al., 2016). Candidates that lower CH_4 production but do not directly disrupt cells are considered methanogen-static, whereas those that also inhibit or kill cells are considered methanogen-cidal.

The method relies on growing methanogens in pure culture in the presence and absence of the antimethanogenic compound of interest, and then measuring the cell growth and CH_4 production by the culture during the incubation. Methanogens require special conditions to grow. They are nutritionally fastidious anaerobes with redox potential below -300 mV, and they usually grow within a pH range of 6.0 to 8.0 (Sirohi et al., 2010). They metabolize only a restricted range of substrates and are poorly characterized with respect to other metabolic, biochemical, and molecular properties. They are usually cultured using Hungate tubes, which are glass test tubes (anaerobic culture tubes) that are tightly sealed and commonly filled with neoprene, butyl, or synthetic—but not gum—rubber stoppers. A gas mixture of 80% H_2 and 20% CO_2 is used, which is made free of oxygen by passing it through heated copper filings. Some investigators also prefer a 50:50 mixture of H_2 and CO_2 (Bryant, 1972), because this gas mixture is denser and not as easily displaced by air when culture containers are opened. The tubes are gassed during incubation or substrate addition and usually have to be injected a gas mixture of 80% H_2 and 20% CO_2 to maintain the appropriate pressure for growth.

Although the commonly used method to test antimethanogenic compounds involves culturing in anaerobic test tubes (Ungerfeld et al., 2004; Martínez-Fernández

et al., 2014; Romero et al., 2023a), a high-throughput 96-well plate-based assay has also been developed using different substrates, such as formate (Weimar et al., 2017) or ethanol (Li et al., 2023). It is recommended to run the test on a suit of methanogen species that represent the most abundant ones in the rumen across the main phylogenetic clades and specific metabolic features (Martínez-Fernández et al., 2014). Differences in the sensitiveness of methanogenic archaea to methanogenesis inhibitors have been attributed to some extent to the varying ability to uptake these inhibitors into the cells (Patra et al., 2017). The genus *Methanobrevibacter*, which is the most dominant member of the rumen archaeal community, can be divided into 2 subgroups according to their expression of Mcr that catalyzes the rate-limiting step of methanogenesis (Thauer, 2019). *Methanobrevibacter smithii* belongs to the clade capable of synthesizing both forms of Mcr (McrI and McrII), whereas *Methanobrevibacter ruminantium* only possesses McrI (Abbott et al., 2020). Therefore, *M. ruminantium* methanogenesis pathway is more limited and can be more rapidly blocked by halogenated CH₄ analogs inhibitors, whereas *M. smithii* has greater Mcr activity and requires a higher concentration of inhibitors to be strongly affected (Romero et al., 2023a).

Advantages. Confirmation of the direct effect on specific methanogens and indications of the mechanism of action is achieved. Highly specialized or high-throughput systems offer the ability to screen a large number of candidates.

Limitations. Slow growth rate of methanogens and a limited number of species that are currently culturable are limitations. Because methanogens are strict anaerobic microbes, its culture is complicated and requires specific equipment (e.g., anaerobic chambers). Limited substrate selection in the 96-well plate-based assays will not represent all methanogens. Furthermore, effects on other rumen microbial populations cannot be anticipated (e.g., on protozoal epi- and endo-symbiotic methanogens and bacteria).

Testing Effects in a Mixed Rumen Microbial Community in Batch Culture

In vitro batch culture fermentation systems with mixed rumen microbes allow preliminary evaluation of the effects on other variables of rumen fermentation (Durmic et al., 2010; Bodas et al., 2012) and assessment of candidates under diverse dietary conditions (e.g., Castro-Montoya et al., 2012) and doses (Macheboeuf et al., 2004, 2008). These systems not only evaluate the antimethanogenic effectiveness, but also allow to investigate the potential effects on various aspects of rumen digestion, such as feed utilization and overall fermentation profile. The approach begins with collecting rumen

fluid from donor animals (source of rumen microbial community) and mixing in a tube or vessel with a buffer (mimicking saliva) and a substrate (mimicking animal feed). The donor animal should be fed a diet similar to that used as a substrate in vitro, to provide a more adapted rumen microbiota if the focus is on that particular dietary condition (Yáñez-Ruiz et al., 2016). As the substrate is fermented, end products of this fermentation accumulate: CH₄ and CO₂ in the headspace of the culture tube and VFA and ammonium in the liquid fraction. At different times during the incubation, CH₄ (and less often H₂) and total gas are measured to assess the antimethanogenic effect; the impact on overall microbial fermentation is evaluated by the amount of gas and VFA produced and, if possible, the amount of incubated substrate that disappeared.

Following the principles of the in vitro batch culture described above, Muetzel et al. (2014) developed a fully automated incubation system for the measurement of gas production and gas composition (CH₄ and H₂). In such system, 20 to 25 measurements of gas volume and composition are obtained from each bottle over a 48-h incubation period, which offers advantages in terms of labor time and details in the evolution of impact on fermentation and methanogenesis over time.

Yáñez-Ruiz et al. (2016) reviewed the design, implementation, and interpretation of the results using this methodology in CH₄ mitigation studies, and Maccarana et al. (2016) conducted a meta-analysis of the methodological factors affecting gas and CH₄ production. The main aspects covered in both publications include donor animal species and animal numbers, donor animal diet, rumen fluid sampling (time, location, and processing), substrate incubated to ferment, incubation buffer, and headspace gas composition. Further technical aspects and associated recommendations specific to the screening and selection for AMFA are included in following sections.

Advantages. Relatively small amounts of compound are needed for rapid testing, and research can be done with relatively basic resources. It allows many candidates to be screened in a single, standardized assay and in a relatively short time. Some time-dependent effects can be initially studied.

Limitations. Adaptation of the rumen microbiota to the compound and persistency of the antimethanogenic effect cannot be assessed. It is also an artificial and extremely simplified simulation system of the rumen environment, where some microbial populations decline in biomass after 24 h, resulting in limited representation of the original microbial communities in the inoculum. Fermentation products accumulate, and the highly buffered medium culture with nonlimiting nutrients may hinder an accurate assessment of the compound efficacy within the rumen across diverse dietary conditions. The

results obtained using this system need to be validated, either in vitro with inoculum collected over longer periods in which the compound is fed to the donor animals, or in in vivo experimental conditions.

Testing Compounds in Continuous and Semicontinuous Culture Systems

Longer-term rumen simulation systems have been developed to overcome the limitations of mixed-batch cultures in which the potential adaptation to the presence of candidate compounds can be assessed. Although fermenters can maintain a more stable and representative microbiota of the original rumen inoculum compared with batch culture (Soto et al., 2013), they do experience a significant loss of protozoa biomass (Mansfield et al., 1995). This represents a significant drawback, particularly for feed additives with antiprotozoal properties, such as saponins, essential oils, or lipids. Consequently, maintaining protozoal populations during long-term incubations has become a pivotal criterion for the success of artificial rumen simulation fermenters. Three alternatives have been shown to be good solutions for separating the solid turnover from the liquid turnover: (1) semicontinuous single-flow fermenters that confine the diet in a permeable bag, with the rumen simulation technique (**RUSITEC**) representing the most prominent example of this approach (Czerkawski and Breckenridge, 1977); (2) continuous dual-flow fermenters that involve filtering a proportion of the solid outflow (Hoover et al., 1976); and (3) intermittent single-flow systems that stratify the fermenter content through slow or intermittent stirring (Abe and Kumeno, 1973).

The RUSITEC is one of the most commonly used fermenters for testing candidate compounds to be developed as AMFA, specially because it allows total gas collection, and therefore data, on daily CH₄ and H₂ productions (Li et al., 2014; Belanche et al., 2016; Saleem et al., 2018). It comprises individual fermenters that are initially set up with rumen content (both fluid and solid), buffer, and feed substrate. This is a semicontinuous system, meaning it has daily addition of substrate, continuous flow of buffer (representing flow of saliva), and outflow of liquid and gases, mimicking an open, continuous fermentation with daily addition of feed, and removing fermentation end products for extended periods. Nevertheless, it lacks the removal of fermentation end products through a process of absorption comparable to that of by the rumen epithelium in vivo (Hristov et al., 2002, 2012).

Regardless of the type of fermenters used, the main feature of fermenters is the ability to monitor the effect of antimethanogenic compounds over extended periods of time (2 to 3 wk vs. 24 to 48 h in batch culture) and

evaluate parameters of rumen fermentation with larger confidence (i.e., microbial protein synthesis, microbial community structure, substrate digestibility, or electron balance) compared with batch culture systems (Romero-Perez et al., 2015). Fermenters allow detection of microbial adaptation to AMFA that were effective over short periods of incubation (i.e., in batch culture, Martínez-Fernández et al., 2015). This is particularly relevant when the possible inhibition of the main methanogenic species might be compensated by an increase in the metabolic activity of other methanogens (Pitta et al., 2022).

Advantages. Allows evaluation of whether the microbiota can adapt to the presence of candidate compounds and offers a wide range of possibilities to evaluate the effects of compounds on variables other than CH₄, including substrate degradation, rumen fermentation, electron balance, microbial protein synthesis, microbial community composition, or microbial taxa abundance.

Limitations. Requires specialized equipment and expertise. The equipment is expensive to obtain and maintain, and it is laborious to run compared with batch culture. The number of experimental units is limited, restricting the number of experimental treatments that can be tested. It has a distorted microbial community (protozoa substantially decrease their concentration), dilution rate (high diluted system), substrate digestion and fermentation, and absence of nutrient absorption comparable to in vivo.

OVERARCHING METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN RELATION TO IN VITRO APPROACHES

This section presents and discusses the most relevant methodological aspects to be considered when testing candidates to develop AMFA using in vitro pure culture of methanogens, batch culture, or (semi)continuous culture fermenters.

Experimental Design and Statistical Analyses

The most common design in an initial in vitro screening experiment, using either methanogens pure cultures or in vitro batch culture, is a dose-response test covering a range of inclusion levels, then narrowing those down to dosages that show potential (Macheboeuf et al., 2008; Martínez-Fernández et al., 2013). However, in batch culture, other factors can be explored in addition to the dosage level, such as the basal diet representing different livestock production systems, or animal species (Yáñez-Ruiz et al., 2016; Garcia et al., 2020). For dose-response studies, a minimum of 3 levels of inclusion in addition to a control is recommended, followed by an ANOVA and assessment of the linear, quadratic, and cubic (with more than 3 doses) components of the response to incremental

amounts of each compound evaluated, using orthogonal polynomial contrasts.

In (semi)continuous culture systems dose-response design is also possible provided that a sufficient number of fermenters are available. In these systems, the number of experimental units for use is more limited than in batch culture; thus, the number of treatments that can be evaluated simultaneously is much lower. For example, to test 3 incremental doses against control using 4 biological replicates, 16 fermenters are needed (Romero-Perez et al., 2015). However, in most of the studies, fermenters are used for a comparison of different AMFA candidates at a single dose, previously selected from *in vitro* batch culture (Vargas et al., 2020). Another point to consider for the statistical design is the random effect of the bath where vessels are placed, which could also be relevant in batch culture if more than one bath is used. Usually, each bath has 4 to 8 vessels (i.e., experimental units). If 2 RUSITEC systems are used, each with 8 fermenters, normally 4 fermenters (2 in each RUSITEC system) are allocated to each experimental treatment. The experiment then follows a randomized complete block design, with 4 experimental treatments (i.e., AMFA) allocated in 2 blocks (i.e., the RUSITEC systems). The experimental unit is then each fermentation vessel, resulting in 4 replicates per treatment.

In both batch culture and fermenters, selection of basal substrate can significantly influence the effectiveness of AMFA (Yáñez-Ruiz et al., 2016). Although the antimethanogenic effect for some AMFA, such as plant extracts, can be more potent when poor quality high-fiber feed is used (García et al., 2020), other AMFA, such as 3-NOP, are less effective in feed high in NDF (Dijkstra et al., 2018; Kebreab et al., 2023).

Selecting Dosage of Compounds

For an initial test in batch culture, we recommend running a screening trial with at least 3 or 4 doses with up to 10-fold increase to ensure that possible lack of effect (from very low doses) and overall reduction of fermentation (due to possible toxicity) are covered. A promising AMFA should have at least one dose that causes CH₄ reduction without compromising fermentation (i.e., reduced total gas and or VFA production). Three doses plus control (zero dose) are minimum to conduct the analyses for linear, quadratic, and cubic effects. The linear-quadratic models approximate the effects and show that effect on CH₄ increases exponentially according to a linear and a quadratic component of dose. As there are often limitations in terms of resources in the initial screening, and the aim is to give some broad answers and enable further screening in a more defined range, 3 doses may suffice.

In general, for compounds that directly inhibit methanogens, relatively low doses are applied (<10 mg/100 g substrate DM or 25 to 150 μ M, Martínez-Fernández et al., 2014), compared with compounds that modify the fermentation profile (i.e., plant-based products). For the latter, 0.1 g or less per 100 g of substrate DM is commonly used (Durmic et al., 2014). For alternative H₂ acceptors, because the mode of action relies on their stoichiometrical relationship with pairs of reducing equivalents incorporated and CH₄ not formed, levels of inclusion need to be greater and wider depending on the source used (i.e., nitrate, fumarate, sulfate); hence, around 0.8 to 10 g per 100 g of substrate DM is recommended (Capelari and Powers, 2017; Choudhury et al., 2022).

The preferred method to calculate the dosage may depend on the nature and mode of action of the additive, as well as the *in vitro* system used. It is important to consider whether the dose is referred to either the DM of substrate incubated or to the liquid volume, as the *in vitro* systems are much more diluted compared with rumen digesta. This is particularly relevant when deciding on doses of AMFA candidates that were effective in batch culture and need to be tested in fermenters or when selecting for assessment *in vivo*. Each calculation would lead to distinct results, as DM content (DM/volume ratio) differ markedly *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Dry matter content in batch culture is usually between 1% and 1.5% (Van Nevel and Demeyer, 1981; Yáñez-Ruiz et al., 2016), whereas it can range from 4% to 6% in RUSITEC fermenters (Carro et al., 2009; Deitmers et al., 2022), and from 4% to 10% in continuous-flow fermenters (Hoover et al., 1976; Calsamiglia et al., 2002; Carro et al., 2009). *In vivo* ruminal DM content is affected by many factors, but it usually varies from 10% to 15% (Waldo et al., 1965; Hristov and Broderick, 1996; Zanton and Heinrichs, 2008), which is 10, 2.5, and 1.7 times as high as in batch culture, RUSITEC, and continuous-flow fermenters, respectively. Consequently, transferring *in vitro* doses that were effective in batch culture to fermenters or to *in vivo* on DM basis (i.e., from incubated DM to DM intake) would lead to lower values than those calculated on volume basis. The preferred calculation may depend on the nature and mode of action of the additive. For bioactive compounds having a direct effect on ruminal microbiota (i.e., methanogens inhibitors, essential oils) the dose probably better refers to ruminal volume, as the additive concentration and the interaction with the target microbial cells would influence its potential activity as microbiota modifier (Belanche et al., 2025; Dijkstra et al., 2025; Hristov et al., 2025). For other compounds that act as hydrogen acceptors (i.e., organic acids, nitrate) the concentration of the antimethanogenic compound could be related to dietary DM.

Testing Combinations of Different Compounds

In vitro rumen simulation methods also offer potential to test the impact of combining different compounds that can be additive or synergistic, depending on their mode of action. This is particularly relevant when combining compounds with different modes of action (i.e., methanogens inhibitors that generate an increase in H₂ in the rumen, H₂ acceptors to yield metabolites with nutritional value for the host or inhibitors of protozoa to reduce H₂ production; Belanche et al., 2025; Dijkstra et al., 2025; Hristov et al., 2025). This was initially tested by Patra and Yu (2014) combining saponins, nitrate, and sulfate, and more recently by Liu et al. (2022) combining 3-NOP and fumarate, Romero et al. (2023b) combining *A. taxiformis* and phloroglucinol, and Vadroňová et al. (2023) combining nitrate and medium-chain fatty acids.

According to Romero et al. (2023b), it is recommended to test the compounds separately first using a dose-response design and then, once the best doses are selected, test them in combination. However, a dose-response of different combinations is also possible if the right doses to use from each product are not predetermined. For evaluating additivity of the individual effect of 2 AMFA when they are combined, a minimum of 3 treatments is required (testing them individually plus the combined treatment). Details on the statistical analysis for this assessment can be found in Dijkstra et al. (2025); recommendations for evaluating the combination of AMFA in animal trials are in Hristov et al. (2025).

Because combining different AMFA may need the activation of various mechanisms and adaptation of multiple microbial populations (affecting degradation of certain metabolites), a standard 24-h test in an in vitro batch culture system might not be long enough. Romero et al. (2023b) and Huang et al. (2023) employed a 5-d sequential batch incubation system to promote adaptation of the rumen microbiota to the presence of phenolic compounds that were going to be combined with *A. taxiformis*, and facilitate their degradation (Theodorou et al., 1987). To maintain the microbial fermentation for 5 d, one-third of the incubation volume was transferred daily from one in vitro batch culture to a new one containing two-thirds fresh buffer along with substrate and a new dose of the AMFA.

Delivery of Compounds

The compounds to test can be included in the in vitro system in different ways depending on the nature of the compound. If the material is available in liquid form, pipetting the experimental dosage directly into the in vitro vessel would be the preferred option, as this is more accurate compared with weighing small amounts. Com-

pounds that are not soluble in water and need to be provided in liquid form can be diluted in ethanol (70% vol/vol) at the necessary concentration to achieve the final dose in the bottle. The use of organic solvents is essential for incorporating small amounts of water-insoluble test compounds into rumen simulation systems. Ethanol is commonly used, and although Morgavi et al. (2004) reported no discernible differences in fermentation outcomes between controls with and without 10 µL/mL of ethanol, detailed data were not presented. Although no adverse effects of ethanol on total VFA, gas, and CH₄ production are expected at ethanol concentrations below 40 µg/mL (Miyazaki et al., 1989), the lack of difference reported by Morgavi et al. (2004) is surprising given the well-documented fermentation of ethanol into acetate (Miyazaki et al., 1989), which could potentially increase CH₄ production through enhanced hydrogen availability (Hino et al., 1992). This electron donor function of ethanol-metabolizing bacteria may affect CH₄ mitigating strategies such as supplanting with nitrate supplementation (Yoshii et al., 2005). Alternative solvents such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethylformamide (DMF) also facilitate the dissolution of hydrophobic compounds. However, DMSO acts as an electron acceptor (Lorenzen et al., 1994), leading to a reported 20% reduction in CH₄ production when added at a concentration of 10 µL/mL rumen fluid-buffer medium (Wang et al., 2016), whereas DMF, at concentrations up to 50 µL/mL, is considered minimally disruptive to fermentation processes (Muetzel et al., 2018). Nevertheless, comparative VFA and CH₄ production data in DMF-free versus DMF-containing controls remain unpublished. The inclusion of solvent controls is vital, especially when using solvents such as ethanol or DMSO, which influence rumen fermentation, and although 10 µL/mL has been suggested as a safe inclusion rate, the specific safe margin remains to be reported. In any case, an equivalent amount of solvent has to be added to the control treatment bottles (i.e., AMFA dose of 0) to discard potential side effects (Garcia et al., 2020). For compounds or AMFA candidates in liquid form, we recommend to inoculate them immediately before adding the rumen fluid to initiate the incubation in batch culture and split into 2 applications in fermenters, simulating 2 feeding times in the day. Candidate AMFA in solid form that is stable when exposed to air can be added into the bottles before initiating the incubations in batch culture and mixed with the substrate at every feeding time in fermenters (Romero-Perez et al., 2015).

When and How to Measure Methane and Units to Express Methane Production

In pure cultures of methanogens conducted in Hungate tubes, CH₄ is normally measured in headspace gas sam-

ples taken every 2 to 3 d (Ungerfeld et al., 2004; Romero et al., 2023a). In RUSITEC and continuous fermenters, CH₄ production is usually measured every 24 h by sampling the gas from the collection bags connected to the effluent vessels (Deitmers et al., 2022). In contrast, in batch culture, CH₄ production can be measured continuously at different incubation times when gas pressure is released from the bottles and can demonstrate how effects of the tested compounds vary with incubation time. Some studies have observed antimethanogenic effects of candidate AMFA at short incubation times (6–12 h) that disappeared at 24 h or longer incubation times (i.e., allicin and diallyl disulfide, Kamel et al., 2008), whereas others observed the opposite (i.e., bromoethanesulfonate and cinnamaldehyde, Pellikaan et al., 2011). Concentration of CH₄ in the gas produced in vitro increases as incubation time progresses (Maccarana et al., 2016; Mateos et al., 2016), and low proportions (<12% of total gas) have been reported in short-term incubations (<10 h), whereas after 24 h of incubation, CH₄ proportion in the gas is usually close to 20% (Maccarana et al., 2016; Mateos et al., 2016). Average rumen passage rates of 0.04, 0.06, and 0.08/h are usually assumed for diets used for low-, medium-, and high-producing ruminants (AFRC, 1993), which correspond to rumen retention times of 25.0, 16.7, and 12.5 h, respectively. Because the effects of AMFA in batch culture can be influenced by incubation time, we recommend conducting a minimum of 2 measurements, the first one being at least 12 to 14 h after incubation started to simulate in vivo digesta retention times. The most common technique to measure CH₄ production in samples from in vitro simulation techniques is GC using thermal conductivity or a flame ionization detector (Martínez-Fernández et al., 2014). Because H₂ flow in the rumen plays an important regulatory role in methanogenesis and AMFA may increase or decrease the production of H₂, the interest in quantifying H₂ in in vitro systems has recently increased (Romero et al., 2023b). To measure H₂, a thermal conductivity detector needs to be coupled to the GC (Muetzel et al., 2014). An aspect that can strongly influence CH₄ concentration in the headspace gas is its dilution by nonmetabolic CO₂ produced from the interaction of protons released from VFA with the bicarbonate buffer. Yáñez-Ruiz et al. (2016) indicated that bicarbonate concentrations above 80 mM should be avoided to minimize nonmicrobial CO₂ production associated with the drop in pH occurring as VFA concentration increases.

In relation to the units to express CH₄ production, Yáñez-Ruiz et al. (2016) recommended using in vitro CH₄ production relative to the amount of DM degraded instead of per unit of incubated DM. However, different methods can be used to determine in vitro DM degradation (Mabjeesh et al., 2000), influencing the results of

ratio CH₄/degraded DM. Moreover, when DM degradation is determined by filtering the batch culture content, it is assumed that all disappeared DM was degraded, and small undegraded particles not retained in the filter are not considered. In RUSITEC fermenters, the pore size of the nylon bag containing the feed influences DM disappearance (Carro et al., 1995), making it more difficult to compare across studies when no information on nylon bags characteristics is given. A better option is using the CH₄/total VFA (mol/mol) ratio to compare the potential of AMFA. In addition, this ratio can be used as an indicator of ruminal fermentation efficiency (Vanegas et al., 2017), as CH₄ is an energy loss and VFA are both the main energy source for the host animal and precursors for the synthesis of other compounds, such as glucose (propionic acid) and fatty acids (acetic and butyric acids). Total VFA production can be precisely measured in vitro because there is no absorption and daily digesta is easily quantified. Expressing the absolute amount of CH₄ produced in in vitro experiments in isolation is not advised, and it should be better referred to a value indicative of extent of fermentation, preferably total VFA production.

Other Criteria to Progress with AMFA Candidates

To progress a CH₄ inhibitor into an AMFA, apart from their effectiveness and persistency toward CH₄ reduction (as described in previous sections), several key criteria must also be considered and met. These include ruling out the variability in the effect, possible adaptation, and any negative side effects.

Ruling Out Variability of Compound. Exploratory studies with bioactive compounds or substances have shown great variability in the observed effects between different experiments, leading to inconsistent results, particularly with those of natural origin, such as plant secondary metabolites. Apart from experimental variability, other sources of variability can originate from the material itself. Variation is due to the great diversity of compounds inherently found in natural products (Abbott et al., 2020), high variation in their concentrations, as well as spatial and temporal inconsistency (Pavarini et al., 2012). The chemical composition, and hence the activity can be also affected by different factors such as storage temperature, light, or exposure to air (Kaul et al., 1997). As stated earlier, the diet (substrate) and the native microbial community of the donor animal can also explain part of the variability.

Persistency and Adaptation. When exposed to AMFA, adaptation mechanisms and factors may contribute to the persistency of the effects. Persistency in the context of AMFA refers to their ability to consistently reduce CH₄ production over time. Microbial adaptation refers to the

shift when the rumen microbial community adapts to the presence of feed additives by favoring microbes that are less affected by the additives (i.e., other groups of methanogens, Pitta et al., 2022) or able to degrade them (Weimer, 2015). Initially, AMFA can have a strong effect by inhibiting specific microbial populations responsible for CH₄ production (methanogens) or H₂ production (protozoa), but over time, the microbial population may adapt to the presence of the compound, potentially reducing their effectiveness, as previously described for organosulfur compounds (diallyl disulfide; Martínez-Fernández et al., 2015) or saponins (Wang et al., 2012). The potential adaptation can be assessed by using fermentor systems that allow for 2 to 4 wk long experiments (Martínez-Fernández et al., 2015).

Ruling out Negative and Carryover Effects. While progressing in testing AMFA, it is also essential to ensure that they do not have any negative effects. The AMFA can affect the rumen microbiome or fermentation, overall animal health, and productivity, or pose risk to human health or nontarget organisms in the environment (Glasson et al., 2022; Honan et al., 2022). Assessing some of these aspects is outside the scope of this work. The in vitro methodologies can intercept some of these, such as negative effects on rumen microbes and fermentation and feed degradability, while ruling out negative effects in animal in vivo are discussed in subsequent articles in this special issue. Other selection criteria such as sourcing and costs, need to be considered.

Furthermore, it is important to consider the environmental impact of producing and processing the AMFA that should not exceed the anticipated positive outcomes from reduced CH₄ emissions. The environmental impact needs to be evaluated, not only in terms of additional C emissions, but also water and land use, and so on (Eugène et al., 2015; Alvarez-Hess et al., 2019).

CONCLUSIONS

The first steps in developing AMFA usually involve finding, isolation, and identification of compounds capable of affecting CH₄ production by rumen microbes, followed by in vitro laboratory testing of potential candidates. An array of in vitro methodologies can be used for this purpose, spanning from examining effects at subcellular level on single microbial species to testing in more complex mixed rumen microbial populations. The mechanistic and empirical approaches for the finding and selection of candidates offer potential to test a large number of compounds but require specific equipment and expertise not often available in animal science research groups.

Different in vitro approaches can be used in a sequential manner before in vivo testing, from simple systems

(subcellular levels or batch culture) that allow testing a large number of compounds, to more complex systems simulating the rumen microbial ecosystem with limitations on the number of treatments to test but better insight on AMFA candidate efficacy. This work collated the main advantages, limitations and technical recommendations associated with each step and methodology use during the identification and screening of AMFA candidates (Figures 1 and 2, Table 1).

NOTES

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Nonstandard abbreviations used: 2D = 2-dimensional; 3D = 3-dimensional; 3-NOP = 3-nitrooxypropanol;

AMFA = antimethanogenic feed additives; CoM = coenzyme M; Mcr = methyl-coenzyme M reductase; DMF = dimethylformamide; DMSO = dimethyl sulfoxide; NMR = nuclear magnetic resonance; OD = optical density; pABA = para-aminobenzoic acid; RFAP = 4-(β -D-ribofuranosyl) aminobenzene-5'-phosphate synthase; RUSITEC = rumen simulation technique.

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